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EFFECTS OF PERIODIC INCOMING WAKES ON THE AERODYNAMICS OF A HIGH-SPEED LOW-PRESSURE TURBINE CASCADE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the unsteady wakes incoming from the upstream stages is of high relevance in modern high-speed low pressure turbines operating at transonic exit Mach numbers and low-Reynolds numbers, for their potential to trigger transition and influence the separation of the boundary layer on the blade suction side.

The aim of this paper is the experimental characterization of the influence of incoming wakes on the 2D aerodynamics of a high speed LPT cascade operating at low-Reynolds and transonic exit Mach number. A detailed analysis of the status of the flow along the blade under investigation and its impact on the profile losses are presented for a range of Mach number from 0.70 to 0.95 and Reynolds number from 70,000 to 120,000 under steady and unsteady inflow conditions. Test were conducted at on- and off-design engine realistic conditions in the VKI S-1/C wind tunnel on the SPLEEN C1 transonic cascade. The wakes incoming from an upstream blade row have been replicated using a set of rotating bars, which shed wakes at engine representative reduced frequency ($f^+=0.95$) and flow coefficient ($\Phi=0.80$). A set of densely instrumented traversable blades were used to sample the surface pressure distributions. The development of the boundary layers along the blade suction side is examined through quasi-wall shear stress obtained with surface-mounted hot-film sensors. Wake traverses were carried out downstream of the cascade with a miniaturized L-shaped 5-hole probe to characterize the blade losses.

The introduction of periodic incoming wakes promotes variations in the flow topology over the blade. The effect on the suction side separation bubble is shown to depend on the exit flow conditions. At low Mach numbers the incoming wakes determine a reduction in the size of the bubble, in contrast this effect is not registered as the exit Mach number increases. Consistently, a high dependence of the unsteady wake effect on the profile losses on the exit Reynolds and Mach numbers is demonstrated.

KEYWORDS

HIGH-SPEED LOW-PRESSURE TURBINE, LINEAR CASCADE, SECONDARY FLOWS, UNSTEADY WAKES

INTRODUCTION

The modern geared engine architecture allows for increased low-pressure turbine (LPT) pressure ratio. This is associated with improved efficiency and a reduction in stage count and engine weight (Kurzke, 2009), (Malzacher, Gier, & Lippl, 2006). Consequently, the design space of modern high-speed LPTs consists of transonic exit Mach numbers ($M_{out}>0.80$) and low-Reynolds numbers (Vazquez & Torre, 2012). This combination of operating conditions introduces new complexity, such as the effect of compressibility, on the already multifaceted scenario that is the design of modern LPT blades. The aerodynamics of LPT blades is characterized by strong adverse pressure gradients on the rear suction side that can lead to a separation of the laminar boundary layer (Ladwig & Fottner, 1993), particularly under the low Reynolds number conditions typical of commercial jet engines LPTs operating at cruising altitude. A significant deterioration in engine efficiency is determined by the losses generated in the separated shear layer, particularly in open separation bubbles that fail to reattach. The boundary layer transition plays therefore a key role in determining the performance of LPT blade design (Mayle, 1991).

The transition and reattachment processes are strongly affected by the unsteadiness carried by periodic wakes incoming from the upstream blade rows (Schulte & Hodson, 1998). A large body of seminal studies is available on the effect of wakes periodically shed by an upstream row on the separation, transition, and reattachment processes in LPTs. (Stieger & Hodson, 2005) showed the evolution of the wake fluid in the blade passage, highlighting high turbulence in the region of the impinging wakes. According to the model proposed by (Schulte & Hodson, 1998) and (Howell, Hodson, Schulte, Schiffer, & Haselbach, 2001) the wakes periodically trigger turbulent events in the separated shear layer, which suppress the separation during their presence. The turbulent patches are then followed by distinct becalmed regions. Observations by (Coull & Hodson, 2011), (Clinkemäillie, et al., 2015) and (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013), amongst others, showed that the wake induced disturbances and becalmed region convect downstream more slowly than the wake itself, persisting for some time after the wake centerline has passed.

The interaction between the unsteadiness carried by the incoming wakes and the blade aerodynamics, as well as the loss generation strongly depends on the blade design and operating conditions. The effect of the Reynolds number was studied by (Schulte & Hodson, 1998) and (Brunner, Fottner, & Schiffer, 2000). They documented a more beneficial effect induced by the incoming wakes at low Reynolds numbers, where the separation bubble is strong and contributes largely to the profile losses. In contrast, reduced benefits, or even detrimental effect, were observed at higher Reynolds numbers, condition at which the separation bubble is smaller, and the anticipated reattachment increases the region wetted by turbulent boundary layer. The effect of the exit Mach number on the blade-wake interaction in modern LPT blades was investigated by (Vera, Hodson, & Vázquez, 2003) and by (Vázquez, Antoranz, Cadrecha, & Armañanzas, 2006). These studies demonstrated that for the tested blade designs the incoming wakes benefit was maintained up to an exit Mach number of 0.90. However, for transonic exit Mach numbers the profile losses showed an increasing trend. The authors ascribed the loss of performance to a compressibility effect, responsible for the shift of the velocity peak towards the trailing edge and for the subsequently increased diffusion. Detailed examination of the effects of changing the velocity distribution on the blade suction surface was the aim of a study by (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010). As for to the measurements of (Curtis, Baniqbal, Howell, & Harvey, 1997), this study showed that increasing the diffusion factor and acceleration rate generate stronger separation bubbles, which produce more losses. Simultaneously, the transition and reattachment processes move upstream, expanding the region wetted by turbulent boundary layer and thus raising the losses. Contrarily, designs with lower diffusion factors show low bubble-associated losses also at low Reynolds numbers. (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010) also identified that moving the velocity peak downstream is detrimental for the performance at low Reynolds number, as it increases the diffusion rate and hence the losses produced by the separation (see also (González, Ulizar, Vázquez, & Hodson, 2002)). Other significant design parameters are the reduced frequency and the flow coefficient. Several studies targeted the understanding of the consequences of varying such parameters on the wake-blade interaction. Among the studies already mentioned, (Schulte & Hodson, 1998), (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010) showed that the balance between the beneficial effect due to the separation reduction and the detrimental effect associated with extended turbulent region depend both on the reduced frequency and on the Reynolds number. Moreover, data presented by (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013) indicated the presence of an optimal reduced frequency for the tested design. The location of this optimum varied with Reynolds number and free stream turbulence intensity, demonstrating that the effect of the incoming wakes on the blade depends on the specific pre-existing conditions of the boundary layer. (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013) and (Canepa, et al., 2021) also considered the influence of the flow coefficient. Higher negative incidence of the wake on the suction surface is determined as the flow coefficient decreases, which at low Reynolds numbers was associated to earlier reattachment and consequently to larger surface portion occupied by turbulent boundary layer, thus resulting in larger profile losses.

Most of the works discussed above were conducted in the effort of designing high or ultra-high lift LPT blades in low speed simplified setups, such as flat plate and cascade test rigs. Data collected at engine representative conditions were presented by (Howell, Hodson, Schulte, Schiffer, & Haselbach, 2001) (Vera, Hodson, & Vázquez, 2003), (Vázquez, Antoranz, Cadrecha, & Armañanzas, 2006). Cascade tests were conducted by (Wakelam, Hoeger, & Niehuis, 2013), (Clinkemäillie, et al., 2015) and (Arts, 2013). The latter studies were conducted in the same test facility used for the current investigation.

The aim of this work is to complement the previous studies, by presenting the results of an extensive experimental characterization of a modern high-speed LPT blade. Tests were conducted in the VKI S1-C transonic cascade under engine representative conditions in terms of transonic exit Mach and low Reynolds number, including the effects of unsteady incoming wakes on the behavior of the suction side boundary layer and on the loss generation, reproducing both realistic reduced frequencies and flow coefficients. The tests at off design conditions cover a range of Mach number from 0.70 to 0.95 and Reynolds number from 70,000 to 120,000. The test setup is analogous to that presented in (Simonassi, et al., 2022), except for the addition of the wake generator upstream of the cascade. The blade profile design was characterized in a steady environment in (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022), where it was shown that the suction surface aerodynamics is characterized by a thin laminar open separation bubble. The present work extends the latter study, allowing the detailed analysis of the modifications introduced by incoming wakes on the blade loading and on the status of the suction surface boundary layer, as well as their propagation on the loss generation mechanisms.

The large variety of tested conditions under unsteady engine realistic conditions represent also a novel experimental dataset concerning the effects of unsteady wakes at high Mach number and low Reynolds number, providing references for the validation of models and CFD. The experimental data described in this paper can be obtained at the open access repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7264761>.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The SPLEEN C1 cascade with wake generator

The linear cascade measurements are conducted in the high-speed, low-Reynolds facility S-1/C of the von Karman Institute. In-depth descriptions of the facility are reported in (Arts, 2013) and (Clinkemillie, et al., 2015). The tested cascade consists of 23 blades with a span of 165 mm. The setup is presented in Figure 1 (left). The sketch represents the cascade including a central sliding blade, the wake generator (WG) bars and the inlet turbulence grid. Figure 1 (left) also reports the location of the measurement planes and the used instrumentation.

Figure 1: Sketch of the SPLEEN C1 cascade test setup with wake generator, including measurement planes and techniques (left). Picture of the cascade in the configuration relative to the current paper (right).

The wake generator consists of a brass disk of 625 mm in diameter with cylindrical bars mounted on the perimeter. The bar tips reach 73% of the blade span, guaranteeing no disturbances due to the bar tip flow at midspan. In this configuration, the rotating bars are only parallel to the blade leading edge when passing in front of the central blade. A picture of the complete setup is shown in Figure 1(right).

To simulate the blade row interference effects due to wake blade interactions, the test section is equipped with a high speed rotating bar system located 1.12 axial chords (C_{ax}) upstream of the blade leading edges.

The use of cylindrical bars to simulate the wakes shed by upstream turbomachinery blades was validated by (Pfeil & Eifler, 1976) and (Schulte & Hodson, 1998) who showed that the structure of the far wake of an airfoil and that of a cylindrical body of the same drag is almost identical at a distance ranging between 40 and 80 times the bar diameter. The effect of the wake generator on the inlet flow angle was computed according to the model of (Berrino, Simoni, Ubaldi, Zunino, & Bertini, 2014). After a series of commissioning tests, the cascade was rotated counterclockwise by 6.15 deg with respect to the tests without rotating bars, reaching 46.9 deg to the vertical axis, to compensate for the turning induced by the rotating bars.

Spleen C1 blade design.

The SPLEEN C1 blade profile is representative of a blade hub-endwall section and was designed for transonic outlet Mach number, high deflection, and low flow acceleration. The blade geometry is depicted in Figure 2. A detailed description of the test-case is presented in (Simonassi, et al., 2022). The scaled geometrical dimensions of the cascade and the details of the blade velocity distribution are reported in Table 1.

Figure 2: SPLEEN C1 blade geometry.

Table 1: SPLEEN cascade design parameters.

Chord, C	52.280	[mm]
Axial chord, C_{ax}	47.614	[mm]
Pitch, g	32.950	[mm]
Pitch-to-chord ratio	0.630	[-]
Cascade span	165	[mm]
Max thickness/Chord	0.1265	[-]
TE thickness δte	0.870	[mm]
Throat opening, o	19.40	[mm]
Stagger angle, ζ	24.40	[deg]
Wedge angle ϵ_{ss}	6.48	[deg]
Inlet metal angle, $\beta_{m,in}$	37.30	[deg]
Outlet metal angle, $\beta_{m,out}$	53.80	[deg]
Nominal inlet flow angle β_{in}	36.4	[deg]
Nominal outlet flow angle β_{out}	52.8	[deg]

Test conditions

The tests were carried out at representative conditions of high-speed LPTs for modern geared turbofan engines. Table 2 summarizes the nominal and off-design operating conditions. The Reynolds number characteristic length is the blade chord. Since the wake generator was operated at a fixed rotational velocity, the bar reduced frequencies and flow coefficients are different for each flow condition.

Table 2: Nominal and off design flow conditions. (F: flow field measurements at cascade outlet; B Pneu: blade surface pneumatic measurements; B HF: Hot-films sensors on blade surface).

Nominal conditions		Off-design conditions											
		$Re_{6,is}$		70000				100000		120000			
$M_{6,is}$	0.90	$Re_{6,is}$	65000	0.70	0.90	0.70	0.80	0.90	0.95	0.70	0.90	0.70	0.90
$Re_{6,is}$	70,000	f^+		1.18	0.95	1.18	1.05	0.95	0.90	1.18	0.95	1.18	0.95
$M_{1,is}$	0.46	Φ		0.72	0.77	0.72	0.77	0.80	0.80	0.72	0.80	0.72	0.80
f^+	0.95	F				X		X				X	X
Φ	0.80	B Pneu		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
		B HF				X		X	X				X

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The cascade operating point is defined in terms of outlet isentropic Reynolds and Mach number monitored by means of the total pressure and temperature upstream and static pressure downstream of the blade row. The total temperature is measured by means of a type-K thermocouple at Plane Ref. The uncertainty on the temperature measurements is ± 0.518 K (20:1). A correlation was built to estimate the total pressure losses across the TG and WG at different operating points. The correlation is used to calculate the total pressure at Plane 01 with a total uncertainty of ± 31 Pa (20:1). Endwall taps connected to a Scanivalve MPS4264 – 2.5 PSI are used to measure the outlet static pressure with a total uncertainty of ± 29 Pa (20:1).

Blade Measurements

The characterization of the blade steady aerodynamics is obtained by combining measurements performed with two instrumented blades (PS and SS). The pressure taps are displaced by traversing the instrumented blade at 66 spanwise locations starting from the midspan ($z/H=0.50$), until the end-wall ($z/H=0.00$). The pressure is acquired by means of a Scanivalve MPS4264 – 1 PSI pressure scanner. The local isentropic Mach number is computed with a total uncertainty of ± 0.005 (20:1).

Surface mounted hot-films are used to characterize the blade unsteady aerodynamics. The blade presents 52 sensors equally distributed on the central blade PS (21 sensors) and SS (31 sensors). The distance between each sensor is 2 mm. The sensors were operated using a Dantec Streamline Pro chassis with six channels. The measurements were performed with a sampling frequency of 1.2 MHz for a sampling period of 3s, corresponding to 165 rotations of the upstream wake generator. A square-wave test was performed at the maximum mass-flux conditions ($M_{6,is}=0.90$; $Re_{6,is}=120k$) to maximize the bandwidth of the sensors. A minimum bandwidth of 50 kHz was achieved for all the sensors. The signals were low-pass filtered at 8 kHz in the steady case and 30 kHz in the unsteady case.

The sensors were operated at an over-temperature of ~ 60 K, granting an over-heat ratio of 0.50. The qualitative description of the wall shear stress in Equation (1), introduced in (Hodson, 1983) is used in this study.

$$\tau_w \approx \tau_q = \left(\frac{E^2 - E_0^2}{E_0^2} \right)^3 \quad (1)$$

Where E is the bridge voltage with flow and E_0 is the bridge voltage without flow at the same operating temperature. Since the sensors are operated at constant temperature but the flow and blade temperature during the measurements vary the voltage correction proposed in (Hultmark, 2010) and shown in Equation (2) is applied to the acquired voltages with and without flow.

$$E_{corr} = E \times \sqrt{\frac{T_s - T_0}{T_s - T_a}} \quad (2)$$

Where T_s is the sensor temperature during operation, T_a is the gas temperature during the measurement and T_0 is the reference temperature to which the overtemperature resultant from the overheat ratio is applied during the setup.

Inlet and outlet flow field

The inlet flow was investigated by means of a cobra-shaped miniaturized five-hole pressure probe located at $0.50C_{ax}$ upstream of the central blade leading edge (Plane 02). The probe is calibrated for a range of yaw (α) and pitch (γ) angles of ± 30 deg, and Mach number between 0.20 and 0.60. The error due to the finite spatial resolution of the probe ports along the pitchwise direction, was corrected using the first correction proposed by (Ligrani, Baun, & Singer, 1989). The total uncertainty on the yaw and pitch angles is ± 1.00 deg and ± 0.60 deg, respectively.

The inlet turbulence measurements were carried out using a single wire probe featuring a $9 \mu m$ wire parallel to the probe stem axis, i.e., parallel to the blades LE and rotating bar. The signals were acquired at a frequency of 1.2 MHz for 3 seconds after being analogue low-pass filtered by the CTA system at 30 kHz. The free steam turbulence intensity is computed according to the sensitivity coefficients method reported in the works of

(Cukurel, Acarer, & Arts, 2012) and (Bouffidi & Fontaneto, 2016) assuming negligible the fluctuations of temperature and density (Simonassi, et al., 2022).

The downstream flow field was measured with an L-shaped miniaturized five-hole probe at $0.50C_{ax}$ downstream of the central blade trailing edge (Plane 06). The probe was calibrated for a range of α and γ of ± 30 deg with Mach number varying between 0.20 and 0.95. The same spatial corrections as for the cobra-shaped five-hole probe are used. Performance results are reported in this work in terms energy loss coefficient, defined according to (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022). The total uncertainty on the energy loss coefficient is ± 0.0083 . The error on the midspan mass-averaged energy loss coefficient computed by comparing repeated traverses is below ± 0.00032 , demonstrating high test-to test repeatability.

A detailed description of the probes, blade instrumentation and uncertainty estimation can be also found in (Simonassi, et al., 2022) and (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cascade inlet flow

The cascade inlet flow is interrogated by means of cobra-five-hole-probe and single wire probe in Plane 02. The main characteristics are reported in Table 3 for both the steady and unsteady inlet cases. The table reports the midspan flow incidence angle and the maximum pitchwise variation observed within all the off-design flow conditions, alongside the midspan nominal pitch angle and pitchwise area averaged turbulence intensity at midspan. The results show a variation of the incidence between the steady and unsteady cases. Despite the attempt to modify the cascade relative angle, it was not possible to obtain a complete compensation of the wake generator effect. This is ascribable to the large blockage induced by the cascade, which promotes additional flow turning at the cascade inlet. The incidence variation due to the change of flow conditions is maintained minimal also in the unsteady case. Moreover, the wake generator seems to have a limited effect on the inlet pitch angle. A time-mean increase of turbulence intensity of 1.74% associated with the presence of the rotating bars is recorded.

Table 3: Comparison of inlet flow conditions with and without incoming wakes.

	$(i_{MS})_{Nominal} [deg]$	$(\Delta i_{MS})_{max} [deg]$	$(\gamma_{MS})_{Nominal} [deg]$	Tu [%]
Steady	-0.89	± 0.24	0.65	2.30
Unsteady	-2.00	± 0.40	0.75	4.10

Blade aerodynamics

Blade pneumatic taps

The profile isentropic Mach number distributions with and without incoming wakes are displayed in Figure 3 (left) for the investigated on and off-design Mach numbers at the nominal exit Reynolds number ($Re_{6, is} = 70k$). The comparison between steady and unsteady inflow cases at midspan shows a significant effect of the incidence angle variation due to the presence of the rotating bars upstream of the cascade for all exit Mach numbers. The unsteady cases show lower isentropic Mach number in the blade front SS (A), consistently with the increased negative incidence promoted by the rotating bars. A zoomed view of the rear SS is reported in Figure 3 (right). To study the impact of the exit Reynolds number, in this plot the comparison is extended to the $Re_{6, is} = 120k$ cases. All undisturbed blade loadings feature a laminar separation bubble on the rear SS, as described in (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022). The main characteristic of the flow topology over the blade rear SS obtained applying the methodology defined in (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022) are reported in Table 4. The location of the separation and reattachment are assessed analyzing the distributions of isentropic Mach number, acceleration parameter (K_s), and spatial derivative of the acceleration parameter ($\partial K_s / \partial S$), computed from the surface pressure taps measurements. The influence of the outlet Reynolds number is evident in the two steady cases at $M_{6, is} = 0.70$ and $M_{6, is} = 0.80$, as early reattachment and consequently closed separations are observed at $Re_{6, is} = 120k$ (B, B'). As the exit Mach number is increased to 0.90 and 0.95, the

Reynolds number effect becomes weaker. For both Reynold numbers, the separated boundary layer does not reattach by the last pressure tap location. Table 4 shows that as the exit Mach number increases the location of the suction peak is shifted towards the blade trailing edge and the diffusion factor is progressively reduced. A consequence of the peak velocity aft shift is the growth of the deceleration rate (defined as in (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010)) registered for increasing exit Mach numbers.

Figure 3: Comparison of PS and SS distributions of isentropic Mach number at $Re_{6,is} = 70k$ with and without periodic incoming wakes (left) and detail of rear part of SS for all investigated exit Mach number cases at $Re_{6,is}=70k$ and at $Re_{6,is}=120k$ (right).

Table 4: Blade loading characteristics for all tested outlet Mach number conditions at $Re_{6,is}=70k$ and $Re_{6,is}=120k$. Locations of separation and reattachment obtained applying the method of (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022).

$Re_{6,is}$	$M_{6,is}$	S_{peak} [S/S_L]		$M_{is,max}$ [-]		DF [-]		DR [-]		Separation [S/S_L]		Reattachment [S/S_L]	
		S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U	S	U
70k	0.70	0.37	0.41	0.874	0.882	0.25	0.26	0.39	0.41	0.54	0.55	0.92	0.80
70k	0.80	0.46	0.50	0.975	0.986	0.22	0.23	0.41	0.43	0.56	0.57	ND	0.87
70k	0.90	0.53	0.56	1.070	1.082	0.19	0.20	0.40	0.43	0.65	0.68	ND	ND
70k	0.95	0.63	0.65	1.120	1.130	0.18	0.19	0.48	0.51	0.70	0.70	ND	ND
120k	0.70	0.39	0.41	0.891	0.896	0.27	0.28	0.45	0.46	0.54	0.57	0.86	0.75
120k	0.80	0.44	-	0.981	-	0.26	-	0.40	-	0.56	-	0.92	-
120k	0.90	0.53	0.55	1.079	1.090	0.20	0.21	0.42	0.45	0.63	0.67	ND	0.89
120k	0.95	0.62	-	1.114	-	0.17	-	0.45	-	0.69	-	ND	-

The unsteady inflow promotes early reattachment for the $M_{6,is}=0.70$ cases at both outlet Reynolds numbers and in the $M_{6,is}=0.80$; $Re_{6,is}=70k$ case (C, C'). For increasing high exit Mach number, the effect of the incoming wakes becomes less impactful. Early reattachment is registered only for the high Reynolds case at $M_{6,is}=0.90$

(D), while the pneumatic data seem to suggest that the separation bubble remains open at this exit Mach number for the lower Reynolds case. At the highest outlet Mach number ($M_{6, is}=0.95$), the rear portion of the SS appears to be only marginally responsive to both the effect of the Reynolds number and of the incoming wakes (E). An important effect of the unsteady inflow is the increase and further shift of the velocity peak towards the trailing edge for all studied cases (F). This is associated with higher diffusion factors and deceleration rates for the unsteady cases with respect to the steady counterparts. Furthermore, the portion of the suction surface after reattachment significantly increases in the cases presenting earlier reattachment due to the unsteady inflow conditions.

Blade hot film sensors

Hot film sensors measurements were carried out to support the observations obtained by means of pressure measurements, and to investigate the response of the blade aerodynamics to the periodic incoming wake disturbances. Figure 4 presents the time-mean averaged distribution of quasi-wall shear stress, sensor bridge voltage standard deviation and skewness along the rear SS ($S/S_L = [0.30 - 1.00]$) for the four flow conditions tested with steady and unsteady inflow conditions. The quasi-wall shear stress of each case was normalized with the average value of the first sensor close to the blade leading edge on the SS. The locations of separation (S) and reattachment (R) reported in Table 4 are superimposed to the plots using solid and dashed lines for the steady and unsteady cases respectively. The hot-film data analysis reported here was conducted according to the works of (Howell, Hodson, Schulte, Schiffer, & Haselbach, 2001) (Gomes, Stotz, Blaim, & Niehuis, 2015), (Börner & Niehuis, 2021) and (Clinkemäille, et al., 2015).

Figure 4: Midspan distribution of quasi-wall shear stress (top), voltage standard deviation (center) and voltage skewness (bottom). S_S (Steady case separation location), S_U (unsteady case separation location), R_S (steady case reattachment location), R_U (unsteady case reattachment location) computed from pneumatic taps data.

The low exit Mach ($M_{6, is}=0.70$; $Re_{6, is}=70k$, left column in Figure 4) steady case is taken as a reference to compare with the literature and describe the evolution of the signals along the SS. The average value of τ_q drops

to nearly-zero values at the location of separation (S) in $S/S_L \approx 0.54$ (A), while the $std(E)$ reaches a peak (A'). The separation region is characterized by low quasi-wall shear stress. According to (Hodson, 1983), the τ_q may be non-zero in the region of unsteady separation since the heat-flux process is not sensitive to the flow direction. The skewness starts to decrease after the location of the peak velocity ($S/S_L \approx 0.54$) as the end of the acceleration allows the transition process to start. Around the separation location, the skewness tends to cross the zero becoming positive (A''), indicating an increased presence of turbulent spots. The transition process is linked to an increase of τ_q and $std(E)$ (B, B'). Following the $std(E)$ growth, a local maximum identifies imminent reattachment, which is located at $S/S_L \approx 0.92$ according to the pneumatic data. At this location, the skewness of the bridge voltage approaches zero (B'').

The distributions of the unsteady case at $M_{6,is}=0.70$; $Re_{6,is}=70k$ are useful to discern the effect of the periodic incoming wakes. The location of separation is little impacted, while the reattachment seems greatly anticipated at $S/S_L \approx 0.80$. At the nominal steady flow conditions ($M_{6,is}=0.90$; $Re_{6,is}=70k$, center-left column in Figure 4) the hot-film data supports the presence of an open separation bubble, as hinted by the analysis of the pneumatic data (Figure 3 and Table 4). In the unsteady case, τ_q and $std(E)$ register an increase after $S/S_L \approx 0.80$ (C), while the $skew(E)$ approaching zero close to the trailing edge (C'). This suggests that the incoming wakes promote the onset of transition also at a higher exit Mach number. However, the growth of the $std(E)$ is not complete and the $skew(E)$ does not reach zero by the location of the last sensor. An important difference with respect to the lower exit Mach case is the location of the velocity peak, which shifts towards the trailing edge as the exit Mach number increases (Figure 3), allowing less surface length to the transition process to occur. Increasing the exit Mach to 0.95 (Figure 4, center right column) reduced the growth of both quasi-wall shear stress and $std(E)$ after the separation location, supporting the inference that the reattachment does not take place at high exit Mach numbers, even in the presence of incoming wakes. The further aft shift of the velocity peak, and consequently of the separation location, observed at $M_{6,is}=0.95$ appears to further weaken the wake induced transition process. At $M_{6,is}=0.90$; $Re_{6,is}=120k$ (Figure 4, right column), the evolution of the distributions in the steady case is similar to case with the same exit Mach number, but lower Reynolds (70k). The periodic wakes seem to promote a steeper growth in the $std(E)$ (D), reaching a peak at $S/S_L \approx 0.89$. The hot-film data agree with the pressure measurements, suggesting the presence of reattachment at this location.

To investigate the fundamental unsteady characteristic of the interaction between the periodically incoming wakes and the separated flow on the blade rear suction surface, time-space (T-S) diagrams of the phase-averaged hot-films data are shown in Figure 5. The x-axis shows the fraction of the suction side between $S/S_L=0.30$ and the trailing edge and the y-axis represents the variation of time normalized with the bars passing period. The instantaneous values of quasi-wall shear stress and standard deviation of the sensors bridge voltage were normalized with the time mean of the first sensor close to the blade leading edge on the SS, to facilitate a comparison between cases. The black dashed lines superimposed to the plots represent the trajectory of the passing wakes obtained by means of the blade pneumatic tap pressure measurements. The time average locations of separation and reattachment (Table 4) are indicated with vertical solid and dashed lines respectively. The lower Reynolds and Mach number ($M_{6,is}=0.70$; $Re_{6,is}=70k$) case (Figure 5, top row) shows similar characteristics to the models described in literature (Schulte & Hodson, 1998), (Howell, Hodson, Schulte, Schiffer, & Haselbach, 2001) and amongst others). After the suction peak ($S/S_L \approx 0.37$), the flow decelerates until the separation region is found at $S/S_L \approx 0.54$. The location of the separation seems to vary around the time mean location in phase with the passage of the wakes (A). Regions of higher τ_q after the wake were associated in previous works to the negative jet effect (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013). After the separation region, the disturbance of the wakes appears most evident with the typical wedge shape visible in all three plotted quantities. The origin of the wedge is identified at $S/S_L \approx 0.62$ as an increase in $std(E)$ and $skew(E)$ (B, B'). Point-dashed lines downstream of this location indicate the traveling path of wake-induced features. The turbulent patches introduced by the wake center are indicated by a strip of high standard deviation and are approximately comprised by the lines representing 88% and 50% of the wake propagation velocity, with a maximum right above the $0.70U_{is}$ propagation line. Several authors ((Coull & Hodson, 2011), (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013), amongst others) report that $0.88U_{is}$ and $0.50U_{is}$ are the velocities of the leading and trailing edge of a turbulent spot in zero pressure gradient, according to the

experiments reported by (Schubauer & Klebanoff, 1955). According to (Coull & Hodson, 2011), the 70% velocity rate represent amplified Klebanoff streaks. This region of high $std(E)$ is associated with high quasi-wall shear stress, which suggests reattached turbulent boundary layer. Between $t/T \approx 0.65$ and $t/T \approx 1.40$, increased values of quasi-wall shear stress upstream of the time averaged reattachment location indicate that the wake induced disturbance generates a periodical anticipation of reattachment (C, C'). Following the wake-induced path, regions of substantially lower voltage standard deviation are indicative of the becalmed region. The propagation velocity of the becalmed region trailing limit is indicated by the line at $0.3U_{is}$, as supported by several works in literature ((Schulte & Hodson, 1998), (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013), (Clinkemaeille, et al., 2015)). After the trailing edge of the becalmed region, lower values of τ_q and $std(E)$ are found (D, D'). This is an indication that the separation bubble gradually returns to its undisturbed length between two wake passing events.

The two central rows in Figure 5 present the higher Mach number cases at $Re_{6,is}=70k$. The distribution of $std(E)$ after the separation appears comparable to the lower Mach case. The wake-induced disturbances seem to respect the typical wedged shape, although they appear lower relative to the respective leading edge values. Contrarily to the $M_{6,is}=0.70$ case, the effect of the turbulent patch does not correlate to a relevant increase in quasi-wall shear stress following the passage of the wake, and only a region of moderately higher τ_q with respect to the values at the separation onset (E). These observations correlate well with the impossibility of finding an indication of reattachment in the pneumatic pressure data for these two cases. The shift of the velocity peaks and separation locations occurring as the exit Mach number is increased, was already identified in the data presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 as a possible cause for the reduction of the wake capability to promote early reattachment. The T-S plots at exit Mach number 0.90 and 0.95 seems to support this hypothesis, showing regions of only moderately increased turbulent activity related to the wake passage pushed downstream on the SS (E'). The origin of the wake disturbance is located at $S/S_L \approx 0.62$, while it is pushed downstream to $S/S_L \approx 0.72$ and $S/S_L \approx 0.76$ at $M_{6,is} = 0.90$ and 0.95 respectively. Moreover, the fraction of the wake passing period comprised between the wake passage and the trailing edge of the becalmed region ($0.30U_{is}$) at the location of the last sensor close to the TE reduces as the exit Mach number is increased (F, F'). If the effect of one wake passing event seems to spill into the next incoming wake at $M_{6,is}=0.70$, occupying a period of $t/T \approx 1.00$, at $M_{6,is} = 0.90$ the wake influence is reduced to $t/T \approx 1.00$ and $t/T \approx 0.59$ at $M_{6,is} = 0.95$. This is also a consequence of the increase in wake reduced frequency associated with the decrease of exit flow velocity.

The T-S diagrams of the higher Reynolds case ($M_{6,is}=0.90$; $Re_{6,is}=120k$) (Figure 5, lower row) are similar to the lower Reynolds lower Mach number case. Comparable wedge-shaped regions can be identified and, contrarily to the lower Reynolds number cases at the same exit Mach number, the increase of $std(E)$ corresponds to a region of high quasi-wall shear stress (G, G'). This seems to confirm the presence of reattachment around this location as suggested by the pressure measurements of Figure 3 and Table 4. The $skew(E)$ T-S suggests that the higher exit Reynolds number appears to promote the presence of increased turbulent activity after the reattachment location (H). Consequently, increasing the exit Reynolds number seems to facilitate the wake-induced periodic reattachment process also at exit Mach number 0.90.

Cascade outlet flow

Figure 6 reports the wake profiles at midspan for all investigated cases with and without periodic incoming wakes. For all the tested conditions, the main difference in the wake profile is associated with the thickening of the wake in the SS portion (negative y/g) (A). This result has been related in literature to the migration of the incoming wakes towards the blade SS. The interaction of the incoming wake with the boundary layer on the blade SS is associated with high levels of turbulent kinetic energy (Stieger & Hodson, The Unsteady Development of a Turbulent Wake Through a Downstream Low-Pressure Turbine Blade Passage, 2005) (Canepa, et al., 2021) and increased downstream turbulent mixing (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013).

Figure 5: Space-time diagrams of quasi-wall shear stress (left), voltage standard deviation (center) and voltage skewness(right) at midspan. \bar{S} (Average location of separation) and \bar{R} (average location of reattachment) computed from pneumatic taps data.

At $Re_{6, is}=70k$ the effect of the wakes seems to be opposite between the low exit Mach number and the high Mach number ($M_{6, is}=0.90$ and 0.95) cases (B, B'). At $M_{6, is}=0.70$ the depth of the wake increases in the unsteady case. Even though the incoming wakes periodically reduce the extent of the laminar separation, the region of surface area wetted by more turbulent boundary layer increase with respect to the steady inflow, as shown in Figure 4 (left column) and Figure 5 (top row), determining higher skin friction losses than in the steady inflow case. On the other hand, in the cases at exit Mach number 0.90 and 0.95 , the wake-separation bubble interaction is pushed towards the blade trailing edge, leaving less space for the wake induce transition and reattachment phenomena to materialize. Consequently, a limited area interested by increased level of turbulence was detected in Figure 5 (central rows). This difference is likely to be the origin of the opposite behavior between low and high exit Mach number cases, as also described by (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010). The loss distribution shown in

Figure 6 (right) obtained at $Re_{6, is}=120k$ shows a similar behaviour to the case $Re_{6, is}=70k$; $M_{6, is}=0.70$ (C). The wake profiles in the higher Reynolds case supports the conclusion that the profile losses due to the increase of friction on the rear section of the blade SS after the early reattachment promoted by the wakes.

Figure 6: Pitchwise distributions of energy loss coefficient at midspan for $Re_{6, is}=70k$ (left) and $Re_{6, is}=120k$ (right).

The pitchwise mass-averaged profile energy loss coefficient is presented in Figure 7. The losses are higher for the unsteady case at both Reynolds numbers. The loss evolution for high exit Mach numbers does not follow the increasing trend shown by (Vera, Hodson, & Vázquez, 2003), as reported in (Lopes, Simonassi, Torre, Patinios, & Lavagnoli, 2022). At $Re_{6, is}=70k$ the overall trend for Mach number variation is conserved with incoming wakes, as the losses decrease by increasing the exit Mach number. For the higher Reynolds number cases the trend is inverted, as decreasing losses are measured as the exit Mach number increases, with incoming wakes.

The loss growth with unsteady inflow conditions could be explained considering that in the steady case the loading profiles are characterized by moderate values of diffusion factor and deceleration rate, generally associated with low loss generation in the separation bubble, with respect to the turbulence-generated losses. The introduction of unsteady inflow conditions moves the velocity peak downstream, increasing the diffusion and the rate of deceleration, hence the bubble-generated losses (Coull, Thomas, & Hodson, 2010). The sensitivity of the profile losses to the location of the velocity peak was observed also by (Wakelam, Hoeger, & Niehuis, 2013). Their experiments at low outlet Reynolds numbers showed deeper and thicker wakes for a blade design characterized by higher diffusion and more aft location of the velocity peak. In the high exit Mach number cases ($M_{6, is}=0.90$ and 0.95) at the lower exit Reynolds number ($Re_{6, is}=70k$), no wake-induced reattachment was observed, therefore higher bubble-generated losses due to the increased diffusion could explain the loss growth associated with the unsteady cases. Furthermore, the hot-films data showed additional turbulence activity due to the passing wakes for all cases. Thus, the increase in profile losses could also be linked to a higher contribution from the turbulent losses.

Regarding the cases characterized by early attachment promoted by the wake interaction ($Re_{6, is}=70k$; $M_{6, is}=0.70$ and $Re_{6, is}=120k$; $M_{6, is}=0.90$), the analysis of the pneumatic data showed substantial increase in turbulent wetted length and the hot-film signals demonstrated extended regions occupied by turbulent spots on the rear SS. Therefore, the combination of higher separation losses due to increased diffusion, and more

turbulent wetted area could be linked to the highest loss increase in the unsteady cases registered at these conditions. (Wakelam, Hoeger, & Niehuis, 2013) reported increased profile losses under unsteady conditions for blades characterized by similar values of diffusion and ascribed this effect to increased mixing in the boundary layer, even in the event of earlier reattachment.

Figure 7: Mass-averaged energy loss coefficient for all investigated flow conditions at midspan.

Furthermore, since all tests were conducted at constant wake-generator speed, the effect of the bars reduced frequency and of the flow coefficient must be considered. Decreasing the exit Mach number determines the increase of the reduced frequency and the decrease of the flow coefficient. Consequently, the number of wakes flowing in the blade passage at each instant of time increases and the wakes approach the blade passage at higher incidence. Since more wake induced turbulence is present in the passage, increasing effect of the wake induced effects is expected. Similarly, an inverse relationship between profile losses and flow coefficient was reported in previous studies (Schulte & Hodson, 1998), (Mahallati & Sjolander, 2013) and (Canepa, et al., 2021). This is suggested in the presented data by the higher difference between the losses at $M_{6,is}=0.70$ (between steady and unsteady cases) than the difference at $M_{6,is}=0.90$.

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of unsteady wakes convecting through the passage of a high-speed LPT turbine cascade, was studied experimentally. The measurements covered a wide range of flow conditions, allowing the study of the effect of unsteady inflow conditions at engine representative exit Mach and Reynolds numbers, reduced frequencies, and flow coefficients.

The unsteady inflow generates modifications to the blade loading distribution. All the tested unsteady cases show reduced loading on the front suction side due to an incidence variation caused by the upstream rotating bars. The interaction with the wakes increases the suction peak and shifts it downstream, thereby incrementing the diffusion. Even though the boundary layer on the blade SS presents a laminar separation in all steady and unsteady cases, it was shown that the effects of the wakes on the separation bubble depend on the exit flow conditions. At the lowest Reynolds number, early reattachment is registered up to an exit Mach number of 0.80, while at the highest outlet Reynolds indications of the wake-induced reattachment are observed also at the highest tested Mach number (0.90). The analysis of the hot-film data suggests that the aft-shift of the velocity peaks and separation locations, occurring as the exit Mach number is increased, moves the wake-separation bubble interaction towards the trailing edge. At the tested low Reynolds numbers and high transonic Mach number conditions such shift is linked to the absence of reattachment even in the presence of unsteady wakes.

The study of the profile losses shows that for the tested blade design the effect of unsteady incoming wakes results detrimental. Considering that the tested blade exhibits low diffusion factor under steady conditions, the shift of the peak downstream and the increase in diffusion with periodic inflow is related to the increase in separation losses. Increasing the exit Reynolds number promotes the reattachment at exit Mach number of 0.90

whit incoming wakes. These conditions are associated to a strong increase in losses due to the predominant impact of the turbulence wetted surface. At low Reynolds number, operating at high exit Mach number results in lower profile losses, since no reattachment was detected under unsteady inflow, and lower loss increase due to turbulent mixing was registered with respect to the higher Reynolds case. The separations of the suction side boundary layer for the tested blade design are not strong enough to generate a benefit from the wake-induced early reattachment, but in contrast suffer the negative effect of the increased turbulent losses promoted by the wake.

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NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
WG	Wake Generator
SS	Suction Side
PS	Pressure Side
CTA	Constant Temperature Anemometry
5HP	Five-Hole-Probe
HF	Hot-Films
DF	Diffusion Factor: $DF = \frac{M_{peak} - M_{out}}{M_{out}}$
DR	Deceleration Rate: $DR = \frac{(M_{peak} - M_{out})/M_{out}}{1 - (S/S_L)_{peak}}$
TG	Turbulence Grid

Greek Symbols

β	Primary flow direction, yaw angle
γ	Pitch angle
δ_{te}	Trailing edge thickness
ζ	Stagger angle
ξ	Energy loss coefficient
Φ	Flow coefficient = V_{ax}/U
τ	Quasi-wall shear stress
ϵ_{ss}	Wedge angle

Subscripts and superscripts

0	Total quantity
1,2,3,4,5,6	Measurement planes
ax	Axial
in	Relative to cascade inlet
a	Area average
m	Metal

Latin Symbols

C	Chord
E	Hot-films bridge voltage
f^+	Bar reduced frequency = $f_{bar} \cdot C/V_{6, is}$
g	Cascade pitch
o	Throat
S_L	SS surface length
M	Mach number
P	Pressure
Re	Reynolds number $Re = \frac{\rho \cdot C \cdot V}{\mu}$
T	Temperature
Tu	Turbulence intensity
U	Circumferential velocity
V	Velocity
y	Pitchwise location
std	Standard deviation
$skew$	Skewness
i_{MS}	Midspan incidence $i_{MS} = (\overline{\beta_{2, MS}}^a - \beta_{m, in})$

out	Relative to cascade outlet
is	Isentropic
Ref	Relative to the reference plane
$\bar{\quad}$	Time average quantity
MS	Relative to midspan

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